

Research Infrastructure Security Community Charter

“To infinity and beyond!” – *Buzz Lightyear*

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Table of Contents

What is RISC?	2
What is a “Community of Practice”?	2
Purpose	3
Membership & Expectations	3
Membership	3
Expectations	3
Activities	4
Workshops	4
Community Web Space	4
Public Facing Products	4
Governance	4

What is RISC?

The Research Infrastructure Security Community (RISC) is a community of practice built by Trusted CI for NSF cybersecurity professionals. RISC is composed of graduates from Trusted CI Framework cohorts, who continue to gather as a community to expand their cybersecurity knowledge, share experiences, and build relationships.

What is a “Community of Practice”?

“Community of Practice”¹ (CoP) is a term coined by Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger in 1991. The three defining concepts of a CoP are:

1. **Domain:** Community members have a shared domain of interest, competence and commitment that distinguishes them from others.
2. **Community:** Members pursue this interest through joint activities, discussions, problem-solving opportunities, information sharing, and relationship building.
3. **Practice:** Community members are actual practitioners in this domain of interest, and build a shared repertoire of resources and ideas that they take back to their practice.

Quoting Wenger, “Communities of Practice are groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly,” which aligns well with our vision and objectives for RISC.

¹ The term “Community of Practice” was coined by Lave and Wenger in 1991 while studying apprenticeships as a learning model. See <https://www.wenger-trayner.com/introduction-to-communities-of-practice/>.

Purpose

RISC is intended to serve as a forum for the community of NSF cybersecurity practitioners to meet, share experiences, build relationships, and expand their cybersecurity expertise. RISC uses the Trusted CI Framework cohort experience as a foundation for ongoing cybersecurity community building. RISC offers multiple benefits and opportunities to its participants, including:

- Promoting continued improvement of the cybersecurity posture of NSF science;
- Building cybersecurity expertise among the RISC membership;
- Building relationships and community among the RISC membership;
- Providing a trusted forum for sharing lessons learned, vulnerabilities, and cybersecurity knowledge; and
- Providing a platform for speaking as a community on important topics impacting the cybersecurity of NSF science.

Membership & Expectations

Membership

RISC is composed of two primary groups: 1) Trusted CI subject matter experts and facilitators, and 2) Cybersecurity professionals at NSF-funded research infrastructure provider organizations. These cybersecurity professionals are primarily Framework Cohort graduates, and include cybersecurity practitioners, IT practitioners, scientists and researchers, project and program managers, compliance officers, and research infrastructure leadership. The membership is diverse in terms of the types of research, size of organization, and geographic locations represented.

Expectations

All RISC members are expected to:

1. Come with the willingness to share knowledge and experiences;
2. Engage in group discussions with respect for others' perspectives;
3. Adhere to any special handling requests for sensitive information that has been shared in the group (e.g., TLP-RED); and
4. Treat others with courtesy.

We want all members to feel welcome!

Activities

RISC members are invited to participate in a number of activities. These activities include:

Workshops

RISC hosts quarterly Workshops for the entire membership. These three-hour workshops allow for community members to share updates to their cybersecurity programs, deep dives on particular cybersecurity topics, discussion of new or evolving NSF cybersecurity policy, and new tools and training resources of interest to the community. All RISC workshops strive to be highly collaborative and interactive, with a significant focus on group discussion and sharing of personal experiences.

Workshops are held virtually or in-person when they align with widely attended community events such as the NSF Research Infrastructure Workshop and the NSF Cybersecurity Summit. A virtual attendance option is also offered for each in-person workshop. Attendance at each event is encouraged, though not required to maintain membership in RISC. In-person workshops typically include an informal social event hosted by Trusted CI.

Community Web Space

In addition to interactive workshops, RISC maintains online spaces for ongoing discussion and community building. These online spaces allow for the community to continue to engage, ask questions, provide updates, and share resources that might be valuable to the broader community.

Public Facing Products

RISC will occasionally collaborate to develop public facing products, including public statements on topics impacting the cybersecurity of NSF science, resources we feel would be valuable to a broader community, and updates on successes the community would like to celebrate. Although developed under the moniker of the entire RISC, any such public facing materials will only include the names of those community members who wish to be listed as such.

Governance

The primary decision making body for RISC is the RISC leadership team. The RISC leadership team includes both leadership from the Trusted CI Framework Team and representatives from the RISC membership. These “RISC Representatives” are selected from the community, and coordinate with Trusted CI to identify topics of interest to the community, plan upcoming workshops, and serve as a point-of-contact for RISC members. The RISC leadership team also evaluates ways to expand the RISC portfolio of activities that would be beneficial to the group. All major decisions impacting the community are made with significant consultation and feedback from the entire community.